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A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF THE GROWTH OF ICT IN THE UNITED STATES AND NIGERIA: 1990 TO PRESENT

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Abstract

The influence of Information Communications Technology has played a role in the growth of the global economy since the dawn of the Information Age. “This has made ICT vital to sustaining global growth in numerous industries. Although the US still outperforms the most ICT advances globally, competition has intensified as the US ICT investment as a percentage of GDP has fallen noticeably and has been surpassed or equaled by other countries in the past decade”. The purpose of this paper is to compare the impact of ICT within the US to that of Nigeria in the areas of banking, education and health care. ICT affects these sectors both directly and indirectly through the ICT sector itself, and indirectly, through other sectors that are powered by ICT advances. To get a sense for ICT’s direct impact to education, health care, and banking in the US and Nigeria the authors conduct secondary research to examine the growth or declines in these sectors.

Key words: ICT, broadband, m-Health, digital divide, endogenous variable, GDP

ICT Defined

ICT (information and communications technology - or technologies) is an umbrella term that includes any communication device or application, encompassing: radio, television, cellular phones, computer and network hardware and software, satellite systems and so on, as well as the various services and applications associated with them, such as videoconferencing and distance learning.

INTRODUCTION

The rapid global knowledge economy due to Information Communication Technology (ICT), has increased business competitiveness, the move towards more customer-driven market satisfaction coupled with advances in scientific knowledge, and the diffusion of telecommunication and office automation have led to a period of constant social change, innovation, and the need for continuous improvement. The development in the technical system of communications, such as international telephone connectivity and the rapid use of mobile telephones, fixed telephones lines, access to satellite televisions, facsimile, fixed broadband access and Internet usage among others have resulted in bridging the digital divide between the developed and developing countries such as the U.S. and Nigeria. The telecommunication advancement has not only turned the whole world into a global village but has really compressed and shortened time, space, and distance. Today, people can do their businesses with the use of telephone communication right inside their living rooms without any hiccups despite the fact that they may be several millions of miles apart. This has provided for greater mobility and accessibility. Broadband is defined as any connection with 768kbps or more of bandwidth in either the upstream or downstream. The industry standard accepts either upstream or downstream rates, as many types of connections are "asymmetric," meaning that they have different data-transfer rates for uploads and downloads" (www.ehow.com, 2014).

Figure 1. Fixed Broadband Internet Subscriptions Worldwide in 2012.

Since the dawn of the Information Age which has now transitioned to the Innovation Age, the influence of (ICT) has played a role in the growth of the US economy. "This has required ICT advancements and innovations vital to sustaining ICT as an engine of global growth. Although the US still leads in ICT development, new technology patents are filed from global companies, causing the US ICT investment as a percentage of GDP to fall noticeably and has even been surpassed by competitors in the past decade" (Ezell, S., & Andes, S., 2010).

In this paper we seek to compare the impact of ICT within the US to that of Nigeria in the areas of banking, education and health care. ICT affects these sectors both directly and indirectly through the ICT sector itself, and indirectly, through other sectors that are powered by ICT advances. To get a sense of ICT's direct impact on education, health care, and banking in the US and Nigeria we will examine both growth or decline in these sectors. Fundamental research into ICT in the U.S. since 1980 has given rise to almost 20 entirely new ICT-related product categories that have become multibillion dollar industries. These include OSs, client-server computing, cloud computing, the Internet, graphic user interfaces, the World Wide Web, Mobile, and broadband infrastructure, to name a few. Such has contributed in the growth of the U.S. economy and permeates through other institutions. The growth of ICT has provided

numerous sub-industries that include, social media, mobile, SMS, and most recently wearable's, i.e. Google Glass and others.

For the US the growth numbers of ICT are staggering. Information technology (IT) industry consultant, ITU.org, reported that worldwide spending in this area was on the order of US\$3.4 trillion in 2010, rising by about 5.3% to US\$3.5 trillion in 2011, reflecting a new emphasis on consumer mobile devices, virtualization solutions and security software (Burt 2010). Figure 2 reveals in FY 2011 the United States ranked 7th and Nigeria ranked 24th.

Figure 2. ICT development Index, FY 2011. Source: ITU.org

In addition, the United States Census Bureau (2010) published survey figures from 46,000 organizations on domestic ICT spending for 2008 (Kaufman and Weber, 2011). As for the case of Nigeria, Africa's most populous nation, access to communication is growing at a faster pace than in other African nation today. In 2009, the total number subscriber base was 70, 337, 600 million with an average growth of over eight million lines per annum, recorded from 2001 - 2009, with more than three percent contribution to overall Gross Domestic Product (GDP). In 2010, the total subscription number rose to 87.3 million, with a penetration rate of 55 percent, according to Biodun coke (Business Day, 2012).

In 2014, the grand total of overall subscribers stands at 127, 960,580 million (NCC, 2014). This increase permeates throughout the entire 36 states of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, plus Abuja the Capital Territory, and cuts across the six geo-political zones of North-West, North-East, North-Central, South-West, South-East, and South-South, reaching up to 90 percent of seemingly 170 million population of Nigeria.

Methodology

The research for this paper was conducted through current literature, artifacts, and other materials to gain insight into the ICT behaviors, actions, and other characteristics over a time period between the years 1995 – 2014. This qualitative method required researchers to formulate the thesis for the paper along with crafting the econometric model to measure digital divide. The US and Nigeria were subject countries for this research and the subject industries were health care, education and banking. The authors considered the demand side economic effects and build a econometric model that would offer an accurate measure of the digital divide present between HDC's (highly developed countries) and LDC's (lower developed countries).

ICT in Education

The presence and potentials of information technologies in almost every human activity is overwhelming. Globalization and advances in ICT have brought about phenomenal improvements and great opportunities for developing countries to participate meaningfully in the global digital economy (Nigeria Vision 2020, 2009). The use of ICT promotes development and improves services in any organization.

Figure 3. Understanding of 21st Century Skills and Outcomes. Source: www.ali.apple.com

In the academic environment, ICT speeds up information delivery, facilitates teaching, creates a social and emotional connections and is a platform of culture of creativity and innovation. In spite of all this, the level of awareness and use in Nigeria relative to developed countries appears to be minimal (Haliso, 2011). The literature dealing with technology and pedagogy attests to the powerful impact ICT can have on the teaching and learning process (John, 2010). Research indicates that level of collaboration and communication are enhanced by the use of computers for knowledge building and thinking skill (Howe et al, 1997; McFarlane, 1997).

The implementation of ICT policy started in Nigeria in April, 2001 with the establishment of national Information Development agency (NITDA) with a vision to make Nigeria IT capable country in Africa and a key player in the information, using IT as engine for sustainable development, and global competitiveness (Federal Ministry of science & Technology, 2001). The strategic action plan provides for a five-year period for the key sectors such as health, education, human resource development, agriculture, private

sector/industry, as part of an integrated approach to achieving national development within the context of the Millennium Development Goals (MDG). The Federal Government 7-point Agenda, the National Economic Empowerment Development Program (NEEDS) and a host other socioeconomic development programs and initiatives are part of the (MDG). According to Adeosun, (2010) the mission statement of NITDA recognized the need to use IT for education (p.iii). In addition the general objectives and strategies recognized the importance of ICT in education, Adeosun (2010) also pointed out that Nigeria has no particularly articulated policy for ICT in education in spite of her strong commitment to the promotion of ICT in her educational and economic goals. This points to policy and program incongruence.

Worldwide the education sector have been affected by ICTs. The process of teaching, learning and research have also been affected (Yusuf, 2005). The Federal Government of Nigeria, in the National Policy on education (2004), recognizes the prominent role of ICTs in the modern world, and has integrated ICTs into education in Nigeria. In terms of ICT and teacher development, the National Policy on Education (2004) stipulates that teacher education shall continue to take cognizance of changes in methodology and the curriculum, and teachers shall be regularly exposed to innovations in their profession. Similarly the National Policy on Teacher Education (FME, 2007) developed a vision " to produce quality, highly skilled, knowledgeable and creative teachers based on explicit performance standards through pre-service and in-service programs to raise a generation of students who can compete globally" (p.6). The goal is to "ensure teachers are trained and recruited to teach world-class standards and continue to develop their competence over their entire career" (p.6). In so doing, ICT was identified as one of the conditions for the achievement of the goal.

Figure 4. Demographic Information demonstrates that among university students in Nigeria more male students (60%) than female students (40%) acquire knowledge and skill from ICT usage. 36% of faculty members are comfortable with using ICT in the classroom.

ICT in Medical and Public Health Care - Nigeria

In Nigeria ICT in the form of Mobile Phone is making its impact. Medical and Public Health Care services in Nigeria is supported by mobile devices identified with the acronyms "mHealth", eHealth", or "Telemedicine". mHealth in Nigeria is defined as the provision of health-related services using mobile communications technology (www.health info). According to a 2012 global survey of 114 nations undertaken by the World Health Organization (WHO), mHealth initiatives have been established in many countries, but there are variations of adoption levels. The most common activity was the creation of health call centers, which responds to patients' inquires. This was followed by using SMS for appointment reminders, using telemedicine, accessing patient records, measuring compliance, raising health awareness, monitoring patient, and physical decision support (Foundation Partnership, 2010). As a result, patients are now using "Mobile Phones" that monitor and transmit health information to

caregivers. This puts people in charge of their own test-taking and monitoring, and keeps them out of doctor's office until they need care that is more detailed.

Mobile phones now supports health care systems in Nigeria by transmitting critical data to the right people when needed, such as connecting to a remote health worker with an urban specialist or enabling patients to call in advance at a clinic where they can receive appropriate medical attention at a clinic where they plan to attend. In the context of chronic disease management. In the support of this effort, Kollmann, et al. developed a java-based mobile phone application called Diab-Memory to enable diabetic patients to self-monitor blood glucose levels, insulin use, intake of carbohydrates, and physical activity. The phone application synchronizes with a website where users can chart their data in different ways to better understand how various factors affect their blood glucose level. While mHealth has matured in industrialized countries, the field is still evolving in Nigeria

ICT in Nigerian Banking

ICT has made the banking sector of the economy to change from traditional mode of operation to better ways with technological innovations that improve efficiency. ICT can enhance efficiency via its use and in recent times, banks have been encouraged the rapid decline in the price of ICT gadgets. Ovia noted that this has perhaps increased the bank of ICT usage (2005). Technological advancement facilitates payment and creates convenient alternatives to cash and checks for transaction purposes. Such new practices have led to the development of a truly global, seamless and Internet enable 24-hour business and banking in Nigeria.

Payment systems in Nigeria are feasible due to ICT gadgets such as Automated Teller Machine (ATM), Electronic Fund Transfer (EFT), Clearing House Automate Payments (CHAPs), Electronic Purse (E-Purse), Automated Check Sorter (ACS) and Electronic Fund Transfer at Point of Sale (EFTPS), which have made transaction easy and convenient. This phenomenon is capable of bringing about speedy operations and enhanced productivity (Adeoti, 2005, Ovia, 2005). ICT has made it possible for banks in Nigeria to provide comprehensive services to their customers, such as access to their accounts via online services. Online services have edge over the traditional payment instruments because it is safer, more efficient, convenient and cost effective for banks and customers. Before the introduction of ICT services in the banking industry, manual processing of documents were used. The bankers were made to cope with onerous task, and the process made business transaction minimal and clumsy. Besides hectic procedures, people had to contend with, banks' customers were made to spend several hours in the congested banking halls often times, in carrying out their transaction (Ovia, 2005). Such deplorable conditions dissuaded many people from banking transactions. As more and more banks have Internet and online real time banks are now able to transfer funds from one location to another without any involvement of facial transactions, thereby reducing the incidence of loss of funds by stealing, kidnapping or other likes. Telephone banking is another area of ICT impact. Telephone banking technology allows customers to have transactions on their accounts by calling a particular number through voice activation, and using a tone pad. All of these have improved the comfort and safety of banking transactions, thus increasing citizens' interest in business financing directly and/or indirectly.

ICT in United States Education

Perhaps no other industry has experienced the rapid growth and deployment of ICT than that of education. According to Collins (1996), education offers the perfect conditions to optimize learning and promote the transfer of knowledge and skills through the use of ICT. McCormick (2004), states that "throughout the world school systems are introducing the use of information and communications technology (ICT) in an effort to improve teaching and learning. Some see it as an opportunity to transform teaching and learning, others to make it more effective or efficient" (pg. 1).

ICT in United States Banking

The U.S. commercial banking industry is in a position that it has never been seen before. The increased competition and the current economic recession starting in the financial sector has forced banks to make strategic decisions and determine what their current customers want and how they can respond. Banks today need to improve their abilities to respond to customers, regulators and shifts in the general economy (Howell, J., & Wei, J., 2010). In addition to the legacy of technologies, i.e. check truncation, ATM's, drive up banking, that have created initial efficiencies in banking many new technologies such as advanced computer operating systems, wide and local area networks (WAN, LAN), and the Internet, mobile banking are becoming significant strategic areas for financial institutions competitive advantages.

ICT in United States Healthcare

Further investigation by the authors found that today's healthcare industry faces many well recognized challenges: high cost of operations, inefficiency, inadequate safety, insufficient access to vital information and poor financial performance. For years, many have called for a fundamental change in the way healthcare is delivered. And while there is yet no clear picture of what this change will be, many believe a paradigm shift in healthcare is ongoing (as evidenced by Affordable care), and that (ICT) is the catalyst (Helms, M. M., Moore, R., & Ahmadi, M., 2008). Current literature in the subject area discuss the use of mobile technology to expedite patient's records, appointments and billing. According to the U.S. Department of Health and Human Services (HHS), approximately 13% of the nation's 4,000+ hospitals use electronic medical records and 14% to 28% of the 853,000 U.S. physicians are wired (Swartz, 2005).

Digital Divide

Digital divide is a term that refers to the gap between demographics and regions that have access to modern information and communications technology, and those that don't or have restricted access. This technology can include the telephone, television, personal computers and the Internet.

Well before the late 20th century, digital divide referred chiefly to the division between those with and without telephone access; after the late 1990s the term began to be used mainly to describe the split between those with and without Internet access, particularly broadband.

CONCLUSION

The introduction of ICT, particularly mobile phone usage has grown significantly in the U.S. and Nigeria over the past decades. Empirical evidence shows that ICT is yet to be fully embraced in Nigeria compared to other advanced countries such as the United States of America despite the rapid decline in the price of ICT gadgets. In Nigeria, while the mobile phone in particular is owned by majority of adult citizens, access to computer and internet system is poor. Thus exacerbating the problem of global digital divide. The state of ICT in Nigeria is still incomparable with the U.S. Out of all the ICT indicators examined in this study mobile phone has the highest number of users, followed by Internet and computer.

Limitation and future Research/Recommendation

There are some limitations in this study that call for future research. The focus of this study is on education, banking, and healthcare systems. Future studies involving surveys or experiments in all other institutions should be considered as our findings do not apply to all the institutions. We recommend using Gompertz Technology Diffusion model as used by Stoneman (1983), and Digital divide Framework (fig.5) for further study to estimate factors that are responsible for the slow ICT diffusion process in poor countries. The specifications of the model are as follows:

T_{it} is an indicator of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in a country i in year t and T_i^* be its post diffusion or equilibrium level or value (T_i^* or equilibrium level of ICT in country i will be a function of exogenous demand side variables).

Most of the models of technology adoption assume that over time

T_{it} tends to T_i^* along an S-shaped path i.e. this model assumes that spread between the value of the ICT indicator in year 't' and its value in year 't-1' is a function of the spread between a target value and value in year t-1.

$$\ln T_{it} - \ln T_{it-1} = a_i b_0 + a_i b_{i1} \ln Y_{it} + a_i g Z_{it} - a_i \ln T_{it-1} + e$$

$$\ln T_{it} - \ln T_{it-1} = a_i b_0 + a_i b_{i1} \ln Y_{it} + a_i g Z_{it} - a_i \ln T_{it-1} + e$$

where e represents the error terms that are uncorrelated with zero mean and s^2 variance.

Figure 5 below provides a framework for the digital divide spectrum.

A glance at Figure 5 shows the presence of two sets of physical and real factors which influence countries access to ICT. Using this framework helps to understand how physical and real factors contribute to digital divide between nations. The exogenous variables to the far right are the constants inputted into the proposed econometric model.

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